

Time-transgressive response of benthic foraminifera to the deglaciation of the Northeast Greenland shelf

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ABSTRACT

Proxy-based reconstructions are imperative for understanding long-term ice dynamics, ecological conditions, and oceanographic variability following the deglaciation due to the temporal limitation of instrumental records. This study examines the response of benthic foraminiferal assemblages to the deglaciation of the Northeast Greenland shelf based on three sediment cores from the Belgica Trough (~77°N), testing to which degree the foraminifera show a consistent response to environmental change. Recent studies from the Belgica Trough reveal that the shelf edge was deglaciated before 16.6 cal ka BP through a stepwise ice retreat, followed by a rapid retreat through the inner shelf, likely before 12.5 cal ka BP. The results of this study reveal the subsequent development of the deglaciated marine environment to exhibit a consistent time-transgressive foraminiferal assemblage succession across the core sites, delineated by three distinct foraminiferal zones. This allows us to further improve previous reconstructions of the deglacial-Holocene paleoenvironmental and paleoceanographic development of the shelf. It also highlights the sensitivity of benthic foraminifera towards the complex interaction between ice dynamics, ecological conditions, and oceanographic variability, proving their reliability and consistency as a proxy. Comparisons with other Arctic deglacial successions suggest the potential for identifying standard assemblages to recognize specific stages in a deglacial succession: Assemblages characterized by the species *Stetsonia horvathi*, *Stainforthia concava*, and *Glomulina oculus* appear as a reliable indicator of sub-ice shelf conditions following deglaciation, while stable higher salinity conditions often found during periods of influx of Atlantic-derived water is characterized by *Cassidulina neoteretis*, *Cassidulina reniforme*, and *Islandiella norcrossi*. High-productivity environments are advantageous for *Melonis barleeanus*, *Stainforthia feylingi*, and other eutrophic species, and these species thus make out a reliable standard for recognizing productive paleoenvironments often linked to ice edges or seasonal sea ice. Dissolution of calcareous taxa, and dominance of agglutinated taxa characterize cold, corrosive bottom water conditions and/or periods of brine formation.

1. Introduction

The Arctic is warming more rapidly than any other region in the world (Previdi et al., 2021), with recent studies suggesting Arctic warming occurring at a rate four times faster than the global average (Rantanen et al., 2022). In this context, ocean thermal forcing constitutes a pivotal driver for the stability of ice sheets and marine-terminating glaciers (Howe et al., 2019; Luckman et al., 2015;

Millan et al., 2023; Rignot et al., 2013; Schild et al., 2018; Wood et al., 2021). Today, this is particularly evident from observations of Antarctic ice shelves where the basal melting comprises the leading ablation process with a majority of the meltwater production constrained to small, warm-cavity ice shelves (Rignot et al., 2013). Ocean forcing also has a major impact on the remaining floating ice streams in North Greenland, where mass loss and grounding line retreat are dominated by accelerated basal melt rates, closely correlating to increasing ocean

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temperatures (Millan et al., 2023). The continued deglaciation of these environments will impact the ocean circulation through enhanced stratification and significantly alter ecosystems (Constable et al., 2023; Lund-Hansen et al., 2023; Meire et al., 2023).

In order to understand the long-term dynamics of these glacial marine environments, the use of proxy-based reconstructions is imperative, due to the confined timespan of instrumental records. A widely used proxy for such reconstructions is the analysis of benthic foraminiferal assemblages, which exhibit sensitivity towards ocean-ice interactions. However, the reliability of using benthic foraminifera to reconstruct variability in water masses is still contested as studies of benthic foraminiferal ecology find weak correlations between species distribution and water temperature and salinity (Davies et al., 2023; Husum et al., 2015; Van Der Zwaan et al., 1999). Instead, ecological studies suggest oxygen concentrations and organic fluxes to be the predominant limiting factors on foraminiferal distributions (Corliss and Emerson, 1990; Hansen et al., 2023; Husum et al., 2015; Mackensen et al., 1985; Van Der Zwaan et al., 1999; Wollenburg and Kuhnt, 2000; Wollenburg and Mackensen, 1998). It is therefore crucial that these proxies are continuously assessed for their possibilities and limitations to ensure reliable reconstructions.

The susceptibility of the Northeast Greenland Ice Stream (NEGIS) towards Arctic warming has motivated multiple studies to investigate its past dynamics (An et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2014; Larsen et al., 2018; Millan et al., 2023; Mouginito et al., 2015; Roberts et al., 2024). Radiocarbon dates from the Belgica Trough reveal that the grounding line retreated stepwise from the outer Northeast Greenland (NEG) shelf before 16.6 cal ka BP (López-Quirós et al., 2024). By 13 cal. ka BP, the grounding line reached the middle trough, followed by a fast retreat with the inner trough being deglaciated before 12.5 cal ka BP (López-Quirós et al., 2024). The coupling of oceanographic variability and glacial dynamics during the shelf deglaciation has been subject to increasing investigation in recent paleoceanographic studies (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a; Zehnich et al., 2020). Based on the analyses of benthic foraminiferal assemblages, these studies conclude that Atlantic-derived water masses advected onto the shelf during the deglaciation, and it is suggested that the variability of this inflow was an important controller of the ice-retreat patterns (López-Quirós et al., 2024). During the Mid to Late Holocene, apparent contradictions arise between the paleoenvironmental reconstructions, where the presence of Atlantic-derived water masses (AW) on the NE Greenland shelf are reported as severely diminished (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a; Zehnich et al., 2020), and reconstructions from the immediate continental slope where benthic foraminiferal assemblages indicate a vigorous AW flow (Devendra et al., 2022). The difference may well be due to geographical differences with the AW being forced away from the shelf due to increased influx of Polar Water (Devendra et al., 2022). However, it still challenges the reliability of the proxy reconstructions, demanding further testing. Moreover, novel traits-based approaches in the reconstruction of past environmental changes reveal primarily bottom water oxygen, but also nutrient supply, to significantly impact the deglacial evolution of the benthic foraminiferal successions across the NEG shelf, adding further complexity to the understanding of the proxy sensitivity (Hansen et al., 2023).

This study aims to investigate the response and sensitivity of benthic foraminiferal assemblages during stages of deglaciation to improve their application as deglacial proxies. Specifically, the purpose is to establish standard assemblage successions that characterize these stages, while also demonstrating the importance of applying well-dated age models in reconstructions. This is achieved through analysis of the benthic foraminiferal responses in three marine sediment cores along a transect through the Belgica Trough, combined with recent insight into past ocean-ice dynamics on the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al.,

2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a; Zehnich et al., 2020).

2. Regional setting

The study area is situated east of the NEGIS on the NEG shelf with Nioghalvfjædersbræ (79NG) and Zachariæ Isstrøm (ZI) being the nearest glacier outlets (Fig. 1). The shelf is up to 350 km broad and is characterized by two glacially carved cross-shelf troughs with water depths of the northernmost Westwind Trough reaching 350 m while depths of the southernmost Belgica Trough exceed 500 m (Arndt et al., 2015). These troughs converge in a 250 m deep sill on the inner shelf near the termination of the NEGIS, forming an interconnected C-shaped trough system (Budéus et al., 1997). The inter-trough areas are generally shallow except for localized basins with depths exceeding 400 m (Arndt et al., 2015). The core sites cover the inner to outer parts of the Belgica Trough, comprising a 220 km long transect, while the trough itself is 350 km long. The width ranges from 34 to 200 km in the inner to outer parts. It exhibits reversed slopes with depths increasing towards the NEGIS (Arndt et al., 2015).

The NEG shelf is influenced by different water masses that are transported by the East Greenland Current (EGC), flowing southwards from the Arctic Ocean over the continental shelf and slope (Fig. 1). In the upper part of the water column, the EGC conveys cold ($T: \leq 0^\circ\text{C}$) and low-saline ($S: \leq 34.5$) Polar Water (PW), sourced by surface waters from the Arctic Ocean and local meltwater from the GIS (Aagaard and Coachman, 1968; Håvik et al., 2017; Rudels et al., 2005; Willcox et al., 2023). Underlying the PW are Atlantic-derived water masses (AW), consisting of Arctic Atlantic Water (AAW) and Return Atlantic Water (RAW) (Rudels et al., 2005). AW is transported poleward by the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) (Skogseth et al., 2020). Arriving at the Fram Strait, about half of the AW is directed westward between 76 and 81°N (Hattermann et al., 2016; Marnela et al., 2013), giving rise to the Return Atlantic Current (RAC), transporting the warm ($T: \geq 2^\circ\text{C}$) and saline RAW ($S: 34.6\text{--}35.0$) (Rudels et al., 2005) (Fig. 1). The remaining AW continues into the Arctic Ocean where it cools ($T: 0\text{--}2^\circ\text{C}$) and freshens ($S: 34.4\text{--}34.9$), flowing cyclonically at intermediate depths in the Eurasian and Canadian basins before exiting through the western Fram Strait (Rudels et al., 1994, 2005). Around 78°N the AAW rejoins the RAW, both of which comprise the lower part of the EGC (Håvik et al., 2017; Rudels et al., 2005; Willcox et al., 2023).

Advection of AW onto the shelf occurs through the cross-shelf troughs providing deep pathways to the warm water masses to reach the base of marine outlets of the NEGIS (Arndt et al., 2015). While the bathymetry of the Westwind Trough allows inflow of AAW, the greater depths of the Belgica Trough provide a greater AW inflow with the predominance of RAW (Fig. 1) (Schaffer et al., 2017). An overall counterflow of subsurface water masses from the Belgica Trough to the Westwind Trough is reported in the literature (Schaffer et al., 2017; Willcox et al., 2023) but is documented to not affect bottom water masses due to blockage by deep sills in the Westwind Trough (Schaffer et al., 2017). The warm intermediate water flowing through the Belgica Trough is able to reach and cause basal melting of the ZI and 79NG (Bentley et al., 2023; Schaffer et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2020). The subsequent modification of this water mass by the low-density glacial meltwater enables the crossing of the sills into the Westwind Trough, giving rise to this counterflow (Schaffer et al., 2017).

The export of drift ice from the Arctic Ocean significantly influences the sea-ice conditions on the NEG shelf. Here, exports through the Fram Strait correspond to 10 % of the total Arctic sea-ice area which is a magnitude greater than through any other Arctic gateway (Kwok, 2009; Smedsrud et al., 2017). During summer, this export enables the presence of sea ice on the northernmost part of the shelf that would otherwise be free of sea ice due to a positive air-sea heat balance (Schneider and Budéus, 1994).

During summer, areas covered by extensive sea ice relate to the

Fig. 1. A: Map of the Nordic Seas showing the main ocean currents: Warm currents (red) transporting Atlantic-derived water (AW), including the North Atlantic Drift, Irminger Current, West Spitsbergen Current, and Return Atlantic Current; cold Polar Water (PW) carried by the East Greenland Current (blue); temperate currents (purple) transporting Arctic Atlantic Water (AAW). The map also includes topography (GEBCO, 2023), sea-ice extension (Fetterer et al., 2017), the Greenland Ice Sheet (Harrison et al., 2011) and its ice basins (Mankoff et al., 2020), and ice velocity (Nagler et al., 2015). The black square indicates the zoomed-in area in B. B: Overview of the study site on the NEG shelf, showing the location of the analyzed cores (brown dots): DA17-NG-ST08-092G, DA17-NG-ST10-117G, and DA17-NG-ST12-135G; the two trough systems: Belgica Trough and Westwind Trough; and the NEGIS outlets: Zachariæ Isstrøm (ZI) and Nioghalvfjærdsbræ (79NG). The approximate extension of the Norske Øer Ice Barrier (NØIB) and the location of Northeast Water polynya (NEW) are displayed. The locations of compared sediment cores on the NEG shelf applied in the reconstruction are displayed (pink dots): PS93/025 (Syring et al., 2020b; Zehnich et al., 2020), PS100-198 GC (Lloyd et al., 2023), PS100/270 (Syring et al., 2020a), DA17-NG-ST01-019G (Rasmussen et al., 2022), DA17-NG-ST03-039G (Hansen et al., 2022), DA17-NG-ST14-171G (Jackson et al., 2022), DA17-NG-ST7-73G (Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022), and OCE2017-GR02-GC (Devendra et al., 2022).

presence of perennial land-fast sea ice at the Norske Øer Ice Barrier (NØIB) near the coastline of Northeast Greenland (Fig. 1), with extensive but mobile sea ice extending far across the shelf. The NØIB provides a stabilizing buttressing of the ZI and 79NG (Reeh et al., 2001) but it has since 1997 experienced more frequent breakups during the summer (Sneed and Hamilton, 2016).

On occasion the coastal latent heat Northeast Water (NEW) Polynya forms at 80°N, covering an area of 44,000 km² (Schneider and Budéus, 1994; Wadhams, 1981) (Fig. 1). Its formation depends on NØIB acting as a barrier towards drift ice advected northward by the coastal current together with the strength of offshore winds being able to transport sea ice away from the area (Barber and Massom, 2007; Schneider and Budéus, 1994). The polynya formation begins in May and closes in September (Barber and Massom, 2007). During its closing period, the locally produced sea ice is thinner compared to its surroundings, thereby facilitating an opening in the subsequent year (Schneider and Budéus, 1994). The NEW polynya constitutes an important productive environment with high organic export to the seabed (Syring et al., 2020b). Its degradation process may contribute to oxygen depletion of bottom waters (Cross et al., 2018) while brine rejection from sea-ice formation may promote corrosive bottom conditions (Rasmussen and Thomsen, 2014). Together, such environmental factors appear to present significant implications for the benthic community across the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2023; Hansen et al., 2023).

3. Materials and methods

The foraminiferal analysis presented in this study is performed on marine sediment samples from three gravity cores, (DA17-NG-ST08-092G, DA17-NG-ST10-117G, and DA17-NG-ST12-135G; hereafter referred to as 92G, 117G, and 135G; Table 1) constituting a transect through the Belgica Trough (Fig. 1). These were retrieved during the NorthGreen2017 expedition onboard the Danish research vessel RV *Dana* (Seidenkrantz et al., 2018). Upon retrieval, the cores were cut onboard into 1 m sections and stored in a cooling room. At the Department of Geoscience, Aarhus University, the cores were split into archive and working halves and subsequently stored at 3 °C in the core repository. Geochemical, sedimentological, and foraminiferal data related to 92G is already available in Davies et al. (2022), while

Table 1
Analyzed sediment gravity cores in this study.

Core	Length (cm)	Water depth (m)	Longitude	Latitude
DA17-NG-ST08-92G	585	583	78°30.054N	16°16.711W
DA17-NG-ST10-117G	410	497	78°57.517N	15°26.966W
DA17-NG-ST12-135G	270	501	77°07.648N	10°40.539W

geochemical and sedimentological data from 117G and 135G were presented by López-Quirós et al. (2024). In addition, López-Quirós et al. (2024) performed a detailed lithological description of the three cores with lithological units being based on lithology, sediment texture and structure, bioturbation intensity, grain size, and color. López-Quirós et al. (2024) complemented this analysis with the use of high-resolution imaging techniques based on CT- and X-ray scans of the cores. Thus, these available data sets are referred to when relevant. Based on correlations of sediment characteristics and elemental composition data from XRF scans between the gravity and Rumohr cores from the same sites, 9 cm of top sediment was lost from 92G (Davies et al., 2022) while 117G and 135G lost 9 and 1 cm of top sediment, respectively (López-Quirós et al., 2024).

3.1. Core chronology

The age-depth model for 92G is based on the already-established model by Davies et al. (2022). Age-depth models for core 117G and 135G are based on radiocarbon dating of both mixed planktic (mainly *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma*) and on mixed benthic foraminiferal samples (representing the mixed bulk assemblage of the sample interval, excluding miliolids due to their potential to yield older ages, as demonstrated in Ezat et al. (2017)). Dating analyses were conducted at the Laboratory for Ion Beam Physics at the ETH in Zürich using accelerator mass spectrometry. In the age-depth models, the usage of planktic foraminiferal radiocarbon dates is prioritized over dates on benthic foraminifera when both are available, as planktic specimens are expected to more accurately reflect the local reservoir age. Benthic dates are used when planktic dates are absent. Six samples from 135G were large enough to be leached with diluted HCl prior to dating for quality control (Bard et al., 2015). The dating of these leached fractions aligned well with the corresponding main fractions, indicating these latter fractions to be suitable for use in the age-depth model. Samples from core 117G were too small for leaching. The dated foraminiferal specimens were well preserved, ensuring reliable radiocarbon ages.

The radiocarbon ages were calibrated using the Marine20 calibration curve, despite acknowledging its limited accuracy in polar regions due to the impact of sea ice on local reservoir ages (Heaton et al., 2020). For this calibration, a constant local marine reservoir correction of $\Delta R_{20} = 1 \pm 58$ yrs is obtained from the Marine Reservoir Correction Database (Reimer and Reimer, 2001), based on dates from Funder (1982), Håkansson (1973), and Pearce et al. (2023). We also acknowledged the recent approach by Heaton et al. (2023) proposing the boosting of reservoir ages during glacial periods to obtain more reliable age calibrations. However, as this method would increase the reservoir age by two to three orders of magnitude, we did not implement it. This is to avoid systematic temporal complexity and potential introduction of new errors when comparing the results of this study to other paleoenvironmental reconstructions from the NEG shelf and slope, all of which apply constant, unboosted reservoir ages (Davies et al., 2022; Devendra et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b; Zehlich et al., 2020).

The unmodelled calibrated ages for core 117G and 135G are reported in López-Quirós et al. (2024), but here we are providing more detailed age-depth models following the same method as in Davies et al. (2022). These age-depth models are produced with OxCal version 4.4 software using a P-sequence depositional model (Ramsey, 2008; Ramsey and Lee, 2013) with k-values of 0.03 and 0.05 for core 117G and 135G, respectively. This modeling is only conducted in lithological intervals of marine origin, based on the sedimentological description by López-Quirós et al. (2024). Hence, the age-depth model for core 135G applies down to a core depth of 217 cm, where a till deposit is reached, while the model for 117G ends at a core depth of 308 cm where sediments, deposited by

gravity flows, overlay a till deposit (López-Quirós et al., 2024). In addition, the lost sediment tops, based on the gravity-Rumohr core correlations, serve as tie points to improve the constraints of the age-depth models, corresponding to the year of core retrieval. The modern age of these sediments is confirmed by Davies et al. (2024) based on analyses of natural lead-210 and artificial radionuclides.

3.2. Foraminifera

The method for the foraminiferal analyses of 92G is provided by Davies et al. (2022). For 117G and 135G, we performed foraminiferal assemblage analyses of a 1 cm wide interval of 28 and 46 samples, respectively. For all cores, the wet samples were weighed and sieved into 0.063–0.1 mm, 0.1–1 mm, and >1.0 mm fractions using mesh sizes of 0.063, 0.1, and 1 mm. The sieved fractions were then dried in filter paper at 40 °C and transferred to glass vials. Using a binocular microscope, planktic and benthic foraminifera were then counted in all fractions and combined, with the benthic specimens usually identified at a species level. Planktic foraminifera were much less common and thus not analyzed in detail. We aimed at counting and identifying at least 300 benthic specimens, despite several samples containing few specimens. In the calculations of the relative species abundances, only samples containing at least 30 specimens were included. Information on counts and relative abundances for each sample is provided in the Supplementary Material. The size fractions were counted separately on square marked picking trays distributed equally by hand pouring from the glass vials. Counts were then normalized between the separate fractions to ensure a representative bulk assemblage.

Both the volume concentrations and fluxes of planktic and benthic foraminifera were calculated for all samples. The foraminiferal concentration is expressed as specimens per sediment volume (cm^3). Initially, the extracted sample volumes were not registered since only the weight of the wet sediments was measured. However, using the apparent wet sediment density, obtained by López-Quirós et al. (2024) through computed tomography, enables this computation:

$$C = FN \times \rho_{CT} \times m^{-1}$$

Where C is the foraminiferal concentration (specimens cm^{-3}), FN is the number of counted specimens, ρ_{CT} is the wet sediment density derived from computed tomography (g cm^{-3}), and m is the sample wet weight (g).

Using the foraminiferal concentration and the sedimentation rate from the age-depth model, Z (cm ka^{-1}), computation of the foraminiferal flux, F ($\text{specimens cm}^{-2} \text{ka}^{-1}$), is then:

$$F = C \times Z$$

The application of the computed sediment volumes allows for direct comparison of foraminiferal concentrations and fluxes comparisons between the three analyzed sediment cores, since sample wet weights for 92G were not registered in Davies et al. (2022) and concentrations were instead based on approximate wet sample volumes of 10 cm^3 . The foraminiferal fluxes from 92G presented in this study are recalculated from Davies et al. (2022). The presented benthic assemblages are based on selected species of well-established environmental preferences (see also Davies et al., 2023 for detailed listing of indicator species in Arctic marine environments) which show a relative abundance of $\geq 4\%$ in at least one sample. This value is comparable to commonly applied thresholds in paleoceanographic studies from the NEG shelf, ranging between 2 and 5% (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Rasmussen et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a). The assemblage successions were also investigated within this range of relative abundance levels but exhibited no significant changes to the results.

3.3. Multivariate statistical analysis

The benthic foraminiferal assemblage analysis is complemented by a principal component analysis (PCA) to identify which species are driving the data variability. Individual PCAs are performed on each core considering the assemblage of selected species above $\geq 4\%$. To investigate the similarities across cores, a PCA is performed on the combined data set of all the benthic assemblages in all three cores, thereby removing the spatial variability between the individual performed PC analyses. In all PCAs, the relative assemblages are normalized to counter the PCA from weighting species according to their percentage magnitude (Lever et al., 2017):

$$Z_{d,s} = \frac{X_{d,s} - \mu_s}{\sigma_s}$$

Where Z is a matrix containing the normalized foraminiferal assemblage of the benthic species, s, at all sampled core depth intervals, d. X is the original assemblage matrix while μ and σ constitute the means and standard deviations of the species.

4. Results

4.1. Lithological units

The lithological analysis of core 92G, 117G, and 135G by López-Quiros et al. (2024) led to the identification of 7 lithological units, LU-I to LU-VII, which are briefly summarized in this section (Fig. 2). LU-VII comprises the lowermost unit in 117G and 135G, characterized by a massive, matrix-supported till deposit. LU-VI, overlaying LU-VII, is only found in 117G and is composed of massive sandy muds containing dimictic-like horizons. LU-V is identified in all three cores, constituting the bottom unit of 92G, and is composed of laminated mud deposits with occurrences of ice-rafted debris and bioturbated intervals. LU-IV is only found in 117G and 135G, consisting of a matrix-supported marine diamicton, also referred to as pebbly mud. Finally, LU-III to LU-I is found in all three cores and describes bioturbated to highly bioturbated massive mud deposits. In these units, the ice-rafted debris content varies from occasional in LU-III to very rare in LU-I.

Fig. 2. Computed depth-age models and sedimentation rates (SR) for DA17-NG-ST08-92G (Davies et al., 2022), DA17-NG-ST10-117G (López-Quiros et al., 2024), and DA17-NG-ST12-135G (López-Quiros et al., 2024) using mixed planktic (green) and mixed benthic (blue) foraminifera radiocarbon dates and a dated shell sample (purple). The median model age (black line) and 2σ range (light yellow) for the cores are displayed. Laboratory sample IDs (Table 2) are shown. Samples excluded from the depth-age models are shown for 117G and 135G (grey). Models are only produced for core intervals with lithologies relating to marine sedimentation based on core descriptions by Davies et al. (2022) and López-Quiros et al. (2024) (yellow interval endpoints). The lithological logs by López-Quiros et al. (2024) of the three cores are included displaying the characteristics of the 7 identified lithological units, LU-VII to LU-I.

4.2. Age-depth models

The age-depth model for 92G (Davies et al., 2022) is based on the 13 dates (Table 2) and extends back to 12.5 cal ka BP, or possibly earlier (Fig. 2).

Five out of the 13 dates for 117G (Table 2) were from the marine interval and are included in its age-depth model (Fig. 2); dates include both samples of mixed planktic and of mixed benthic foraminifera. Samples from outside the marine interval were omitted from the model. Notably, among these excluded dates are 4 samples from 272 to 329 cm core depth which exhibit highly variable and young ages (Table 2). These samples were excessively small, consisting of only few specimens, and it is likely that the cause of these outliers stems from contamination by younger material during sample preparation.

For the 135G age-depth model, 7 radiocarbon dates are included, consisting of both mixed benthic and mixed planktic foraminiferal aliquots. Dates from the bottom till deposit are excluded. The results of the age-depth models show that 135G and 117G extend back to 18.0 cal ka BP and 12.7 cal ka BP, respectively (Fig. 2).

4.3. Foraminifera

The benthic foraminiferal analysis of core 117G was based on 28 samples yielding in the identification of 42 species (32 calcareous and 10 agglutinated) while 53 species (32 calcareous and 21 agglutinated) were identified in 135G based on the analysis of 46 samples (see Supplementary Table S1 for identified foraminiferal taxa). For 92G, Davies et al. (2022) identified 97 (75 calcareous and 22 agglutinated) species in 98 samples which generally also had higher specimens counts. Both the calcareous and agglutinated species were well preserved in the cores with no to only minor signs of test dissolution. Common for all cores is the presence of a calcareous benthic foraminiferal assemblage in the lower marine intervals of the cores characterized by *Cassidulina neoteretis*, *Cassidulina reniforme*, and *Stetsonia horvathi*, followed by an interval dominated by *Melonis barleeanus*, *Stainforthia feylingi*, and *Elphidium clavatum* (Fig. 3). In cores 92G and 135G, the top of the cores is dominated by agglutinated specimens. The upper 13 samples of 117G, covering a time interval of 0.9–6.5 cal ka BP, were very scarce in benthic specimens, resulting in counts being well below the counting threshold. However, these samples were dominated by agglutinated specimens, thereby resembling the prevalence of agglutinated fauna in the top samples of the other two cores (Fig. 3).

4.4. Principal component analyses

The benthic foraminiferal assemblage successions were subjected to individual Principal Component (PC) analyses with the two first PCs accounting for a cumulative variability of at least 36 % (Fig. 4). Common for both 92G and 135G is that the agglutinated species cluster together, comprising high positive loading scores towards PC1. In contrast, nearly all calcareous species contribute with negative loading scores to PC1 with the main contributors being *C. neoteretis*, *C. reniforme*, and *I. norcrossi*. For PC2 in 92G and 135G, high positive loading scores are related to *M. barleeanus* while *E. arctica* exhibits high positive for PC2 in 135G and intermediate negative loading scores in 92G. Also common for these cores are *S. horvathi* and *S. concava* displaying intermediate to high negative contributions to PC2.

In the PCA of 117G, the upper 13 samples are excluded from the PCA due to the specimen count being below the counting threshold. Hence, the PCA is only performed on an assemblage succession consisting of calcareous species, thereby changing the PC loading scores when compared to 92G and 135G. Here, the positive contributors to PC1 are the isolated, high-scoring *Cassidulina reniforme* and the species cluster related to *Nonionella* spp., *Stainforthia concava*, *Stetsonia horvathi*, and *Islandiella norcrossi* (Fig. 4). High negative loading scores to PC1 are exhibited by *Elphidium clavatum*, *Pullenia osloensis*, and *Melonis*

barleeanus. PC2 is positively driven by *Epistominella vitrea* and *Epistominella arctica* while the main negative contributors are *Cibicides lobatulus* and *Cassidulina neoteretis* (Fig. 4).

PC1 and PC2 of core 135G and 92G display similarly pronounced variability throughout the deglacial and Holocene (Fig. 3). In both cores, PC1 transitions from negative loading scores to near zero and positive loading scores, reflecting the overall assemblage transition from calcareous to agglutinated species. This transition occurs at 10.0 cal ka BP and at 8.0 cal ka BP for 135G and 92G, respectively. Concurring with this transition is an increase of PC2 from near zero loading scores to high positive scores, followed by another decrease to constant near zero loading scores (Fig. 3). The increase in PC2 reflects the temporal change in the calcareous fauna where the dominance of *C. neoteretis*, *C. reniforme*, *I. norcrossi*, *S. horvathi*, and *S. concava* is replaced by species such as *Alabaminella weddellensis*, *M. barleeanus*, *S. feylingi*, and *E. clavatum*. The calcareous-agglutinated transition is not present in 117G and thus the PCs only reflect temporal changes in the calcareous fauna (Fig. 4). Here, a maximum negative loading score for PC1 occurs at 8.5 cal ka BP in between the calcareous-agglutinated transitions for core 135G and 92G (Fig. 3). This score is driven by similar species as for the positive loading scores to PC2 in 135G and 92G (Fig. 4).

In the combined PCA, the upper 13 samples of 117G, dominated by agglutinated foraminifera, are included to represent a calcareous-agglutinated fauna transition despite being below the counting threshold (Fig. 3). The combined PCA yields the calcareous species *M. barleeanus*, *Buccella frigida*, *E. clavatum*, and *Pullenia osloensis* are the main positive drivers of PC1 while *C. neoteretis*, *S. horvathi*, and *Glomulina oculus* comprise its negative contributors (Fig. 4). The agglutinated species cluster closely along the positive axis of PC2 while most of the calcareous species provide negative loading scores, predominated by *C. neoteretis* and *C. reniforme*. These PCs have almost equal importance in explaining the data variability with PC1 accounting for 16 % and PC2 for 13 % while the remaining PCs are below 9 %.

Based on this PCA, the scores of PC1, relating to changes in species composition within the calcareous-dominated assemblages, and PC2, reflecting the transition from calcareous to agglutinated-dominated assemblages, exhibit a similar variability across the core sites (Fig. 5). Changes in calcareous-dominated assemblages are particularly highlighted by PC1 reaching global maximum values initially in 135G at 10.8 cal ka BP. This is followed by successive peaks in 117G and 92G at 8.5 cal ka BP and 7.9 cal ka BP, respectively. Similarly, a successive transition towards agglutinated-dominated assemblages is indicated by PC2 consecutively crossing zero and increasing to positive values with local maxima reached at 7.0 cal ka BP in 135G, 6.0 cal ka BP in 117G, and 5.5 cal ka BP in 92G.

4.5. Foraminiferal zonation

The results of the combined PCA are compared with the assemblage data and lithological units to establish three major benthic foraminiferal assemblage zones (FAZ-A to C) that collectively describe the assemblage development in all three analyzed cores with emphasis on characterizing the abundance of common occurring species (Fig. 5). The timing of the lowermost zone (FAZ-C) in each core (Table 3) is determined by low PC1 values and by the abundance of glaciomarine and AW indicator species. In core 117G and 135G, the termination of FAZ-C coincides with the transition between LU-IV and LU-III. FAZ-B initiates as PC1 scores increase together with the increasing abundance of nutrient-dependent species. FAZ-A is defined by the rising abundance of agglutinated species combined with increasing PC2 scores after successively crossing the zero value.

4.5.1. FAZ-C

FAZ-C is characterized by a total dominance of calcareous benthic foraminifera as agglutinated species are almost absent throughout the zone (Fig. 3). Both the benthic and planktic fluxes reach their peak

Table 2

Radiocarbon dates from core 92G (Davies et al., 2022), 117G (López-Quirós et al., 2024), and 135G (López-Quirós et al., 2024). The modeled ages for 92G are based Davies et al. (2022). Age-depth modeling for 117G and 135G is performed using the OxCal v4.4 (Ramsey, 2008; Ramsey and Lee, 2013), based on the Marine20 calibration curve (Heaton et al., 2020). The calibration applies a constant marine reservoir age of $\Delta R_{20} = 1 \pm 58$ yrs, obtained from the Marine Reservoir Correction Database (Reimer and Reimer, 2001), from Funder (1982), Håkansson (1973) and Pearce et al. (2023). Numbers in bold mark the modeled calibrated median ages included in the depth-age models while non-bolded numbers indicate unmodeled calibrated median ages.

Sample depth midpoint (cm)	LAB ID (ETH)	Fraction	Material	14C age (yr BP)	Unmodelled calibrated age range, 2σ	Median age (cal. yr. BP)	Reference
DA17-NG-ST08-092G							
0.5	113890	Main fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	595 ± 50	528–657	597	Davies et al. (2022)
0.5	113883	Main fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	920 ± 60	695–953	829	Davies et al. (2022)
60.5	110856	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	7120 ± 80	7752–8166	7940	Davies et al. (2022)
60.5	110857	Main fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	7130 ± 60	7793–8156	7946	Davies et al. (2022)
90.5	110858	Main fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	8220 ± 70	9012–9414	9192	Davies et al. (2022)
90.5	110859	Main fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	7865 ± 60	8540–8984	8670	Davies et al. (2022)
130.5	110861	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	8495 ± 80	9293–9659	9492	Davies et al. (2022)
130.5	110860	Main fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	8505 ± 70	9310–9658	9495	Davies et al. (2022)
186.5	95393	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	8855 ± 70	9687–10189	9919	Davies et al. (2022)
240.5	110863	Main Fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	9195 ± 70	10232–10560	10367	Davies et al. (2022)
240.5	110862	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera	9090 ± 70	9967–10496	10284	Davies et al. (2022)
320.5	110864	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	9680 ± 70	10774–11235	11067	Davies et al. (2022)
320.5	110865	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera	9400 ± 70	10410–11067	10748	Davies et al. (2022)
340.5	95394	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	9710 ± 80	10773–11255	11043	Davies et al. (2022)
361	113884	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	10480 ± 160	11834–12737	12338	Davies et al. (2022)
406	113885	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	10080 ± 120	11240–12425	11640	Davies et al. (2022)
451.5	113886	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	10180 ± 120	11336–12466	12074	Davies et al. (2022)
452.5	113889	No leach	Shell fragment	10220 ± 130	11355–12480	12062	Davies et al. (2022)
464.5	95395	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	10490 ± 270	12099–12688	12261	Davies et al. (2022)
470.5	113887	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	21890 ± 380	25389–27163	25120	Davies et al. (2022)
486.5	113888	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	10200 ± 190	11268–12595	12473	Davies et al. (2022)
DA17-NG-ST10-117G							
68	121068.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	6767 ± 71	7429–7835	7621	This study
68	121069.1.1	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera	5921 ± 68	6490–7000	6751	This study
88	121070.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	8312 ± 88	9009–9535	9312	This study
98	121071.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	9400 ± 89	10250–11145	10636	This study
98	121072.1.1	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera	9317 ± 80	10231–11068	10511	This study
108	121073.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	10276 ± 83	11404–12613	11831	This study
125	121074.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera + ostracods	10496 ± 132	11737–12823	12385	This study
125	121075.1.1	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera	10068 ± 103	11202–12449	11876	This study
140	127733.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	19117 ± 482	21456–25011	23125	This study
272	127734.1.1	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera (very small)	10226 ± 290	10698–13069	11944	This study
329	127735.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera (very small)	8572 ± 315	8424–10808	9624	This study
329	127730.1.1	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera (very small)	4467 ± 75	4838–5455	5114	This study
329	134416.1.1	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera (very small)	1195 ± 103	788–1377	1113	This study
DA17-NG-ST12-135G							
65.5	126101.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	2654 ± 88	2356–3075	2781	This study
90.5	121065.1.1	No leach	Mixed planktic foraminifera	8759 ± 125	9454–10247	9853	This study
100.5	121054.1.1	Main fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	8914 ± 92	9547–10297	10009	This study
100.5	121054.2.1	Leach fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	9085 ± 128	9602–10738	10252	This study

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Sample depth midpoint (cm)	LAB ID (ETH)	Fraction	Material	14C age (yr BP)	Unmodelled calibrated age range, 2σ	Median age (cal. yr. BP)	Reference
100.5	121080.1.1	Main fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	8973 ± 82	9667–10487	10073	This study
100.5	121080.2.1	Leach fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	8976 ± 180	9473–10785	10056	This study
120.5	121055.1.1	Main fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	11575 ± 89	13175–13751	13434	This study
120.5	121055.2.1	Leach fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	11370 ± 118	12909–13594	13259	This study
120.5	121066.1.1	Main fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	10839 ± 83	12621–13082	12793	This study
120.5	121066.2.1	Leach fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	11088 ± 111	12741–13300	12991	This study
140.5	121056.1.1	Main fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	13401 ± 99	15691–16601	16133	This study
140.5	121056.2.1	Leach fraction	Mixed benthic foraminifera	13983 ± 135	16321–17526	16990	This study
140.5	121067.1.1	Main fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	13474 ± 121	15707–16882	16217	This study
140.5	121067.2.1	Leach fraction	Mixed planktic foraminifera	13793 ± 130	16164–17336	16727	This study
170.5	121064.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	14069 ± 128	16525–7785	17084	This study
210.5	121063.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	14453 ± 216	16743–18607	17771	This study
223.5	126102.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	24839 ± 649	27375–31091	29123	This study
275.5	126103.1.1	No leach	Mixed benthic foraminifera	46968 ± 4216	43378 – >55000	50046	This study

values in the middle of the zone, replaced by a decrease towards the end. Main common occurring species include *C. neoteretis*, *C. reniforme*, *I. norcrossi*, *C. lobatulus* and *Triloculina trihedra*, all with fluctuating abundances throughout the zone. Other abundant species, including *S. horvathi*, *S. concava*, *G. oculus*, and *Epistominella arctica*, peak early in the zone and are followed by an overall gradual decrease. The abundance of *M. barleeanus*, *Stainforthia feylingi*, *E. clavatum* are generally low though isolated peaks of increased appearance occur. These species display a slight increase at the zone end.

4.5.2. FAZ-B

The initiation of FAZ-B is subject to the near disappearance of *S. horvathi*, *S. concava*, *G. oculus*, *E. arctica*, and *T. trihedra* (Fig. 3). Concurrently, *C. neoteretis*, *C. reniforme*, *I. norcrossi*, and *C. lobatulus* fluctuate at the start, followed by a rapid decrease leading to low abundances throughout the zone. This decrease coincides with a significant drop in the benthic and planktic foraminiferal fluxes. Species of emerging abundance include *M. barleeanus*, *S. feylingi*, *E. clavatum*, *B. frigida*, and *A. weddellensis* which peak in the middle of the zone, before gradually decreasing and nearly disappearing by the end of FAZ-B or the start of FAZ-A. By the end of FAZ-B, agglutinated species are observed to increasingly predominate the benthic assemblages.

4.5.3. FAZ-A

In FAZ-C, the benthic and planktic fluxes achieve their lowest values and remain constantly low (Fig. 3). The benthic assemblages are characterized by a fluctuating and predominating agglutinated fauna with the most common abundant species including *Ammoglobigerina globigeriniformis*, *Portatrochammina bipolaris*, *Lagenammina difflugiformis*, and *Cribostrumoides subglobosa*. Despite occasional peaks, the abundance of calcareous species is generally low, and primarily limited to *C. neoteretis*, *C. reniforme*, *I. norcrossi*, and *S. horvathi*. There is also a very scarce presence of *C. lobatulus* and *T. trihedra* but without any noticeable peaks occurring within this zone.

5. Discussion

The foraminiferal assemblage zones are first discussed in relation to former reconstruction of past environmental and paleoceanographic changes on the NEG shelf. This discussion is combined with recent insights into past ice-retreat dynamics in the Belgica Trough, sea-ice

reconstructions, and past variations in the ecological traits of benthic foraminiferal successions on the shelf, providing a comprehensive reiteration of the former reconstructions. This reiteration serves as a foundation for first evaluating the performance of benthic foraminifera as a proxy for recognizing specific stages in deglacial successions. This is then followed by a more detailed discussion of indicator species as key constituents in standard assemblages for the characterization of these stages, with comparisons drawn from paleo studies across Greenland, the Canadian Arctic, and the Svalbard-Barents Sea region.

5.1. FAZ-C: proximal ice-shelf environment

5.1.1. Indicator species for proximal glaciomarine environment

Following the deglaciation of the core sites, the initiation of FAZ-C coincides with the deposition of LU-V (Fig. 5). This unit is mainly composed of laminated muds concluded to be formed through terrigenous suspension settling from meltwater plumes in a grounding line proximal setting located beneath a floating ice shelf (López-Quirós et al., 2024). The timing of this environmental setting aligns with the FAZ-C which is characterized by the abundance of the glaciomarine indicator species *S. horvathi*, *S. concava*, and *G. oculus* (Fig. 3). *S. horvathi* is a common species found beneath floating ice tongues and in environments characterized by extensive sea-ice coverage (Jennings et al., 2020a; Wollenburg and Kuhnt, 2000; Wollenburg and Mackensen, 1998). It appears across the modern configuration of the NEG shelf where it is mostly dominant on the inner shelf near the 79NG (Davies et al., 2023), hosting near perennial ice (Davies et al., 2024). *S. concava* and *G. oculus* are likewise considered to be indicators of glacier-proximal marine conditions (Davies et al., 2023; Jennings et al., 2020b; Korsun and Hald, 2000), with all three species today exhibiting a similar distribution across the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2023). The glaciomarine characteristics of FAZ-C occur in multiple sediment cores (DA17-NG-ST08-092G, DA17-NG-ST03-039, DA17-NG-ST14-171G, PS100-198, DA17-NG-ST7-73G, PS100/270; Fig. 1) from the NEG shelf during their respective stages of deglaciation (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a).

Across the core sites the ecological traits of the assemblages in FAZ-C point towards a benthic environment of low food supply and oxic to suboxic bottom waters (Hansen et al., 2023). In particular, *S. horvathi* is tolerant of very low trophic conditions (Jennings et al., 2020a; Wollenburg and Kuhnt, 2000; Wollenburg and Mackensen, 1998) while

Fig. 3. The benthic foraminiferal assemblage succession for core DA17-NG-ST08-92G (Davies et al., 2022), DA17-NG-ST10-117G, and DA17-NG-ST12-135G, comprising the transect analysis across the Belgica Trough. The relative abundances of chosen indicator species are displayed along with the benthic concentrations, benthic fluxes, and planktic fluxes. The environmental preferences of calcareous species are colored: high salinity (yellow), strong current (pink) Atlantic Water (red), chilled Atlantic Water (orange), glaciomarine (light blue), and nutrient-dependent (green). The abundance of agglutinated taxa is also included (grey). The first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) from the individual principal component analyses of each core are shown. The time range of the lithological units (LU-I to V), defined by López-Quiros et al. (2024) for the three cores, are indicated. The benthic foraminiferal assemblage zones (FAZ-A to C) are defined based on assemblage variability, lithological units, and combined principal component analysis (Fig. 5). The black-shaded area covering the 13 top samples of 117G marks the dominance of agglutinated species despite the foraminiferal counts being below the counting threshold. Abbreviations: LGM: Last Glacial Maximum; H1: Heinrich Stadial 1; B-A: Bølling-Allerød; YD: Younger Dryas.

C. lobatulus, *E. arctica*, *G. oculus*, and also *S. horvathi* are classified in Hansen et al. (2023) to prefer well-oxygenated bottom waters. These traits are indicative of a low productive environment located beneath the ice shelf. Consequently, low levels of organic matter export and degradation are present, resulting in higher levels of bottom water oxygen (Hansen et al., 2023; Van Der Zwaan et al., 1999). Nutrient delivery was likely facilitated by entrainment of nutrient-rich bottom water within upwelling, low-density subglacial meltwater plumes (cf. Meire et al., 2023). Variations in this upwelling may have played a crucial role for the foraminiferal fluxes (Van Der Zwaan et al., 1999) while also promoting the isolated peak occurrences of species like

S. feylingi, which is linked to higher nutrient levels (Knudsen and Seidenkrantz, 1994; Seidenkrantz, 2013) and *E. clavatum* which tolerates unstable conditions but is also associated with productive regions on the modern-day NEG shelf (Ahrens et al., 1997; Davies et al., 2023). The high abundance of *E. arctica* in this zone may appear incongruous, as it is associated with environments characterized by mobile sea ice and high input of phytodetritus (Jennings et al., 2020a; Wollenburg and Mackensen, 1998). However, its co-abundance with *S. horvathi* is found in multiple early deglacial assemblages located across the NEG shelf, suggesting its adaptability to a sub-ice shelf environment. This is also indicated by the combined PCA, where *E. arctica* is centered between the

Fig. 4. PCA biplots showing benthic foraminiferal loading scores on PC1 and PC2 for the individual and combined core analyses. Explained variability is provided in brackets. The same color-coding is applied to the species as in Fig. 3. The normalized score of each sample interval is plotted as colored dots.

other glaciomarine indicators and the productivity indicators, implying affinity to both environments (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a).

5.1.2. Glacial-deglacial transition in the Belgica Trough – lithological inferences

In core 135G the glacial-deglacial transition is recorded with deposition of LU-V superimposing the glacial till deposit of LU-VII (Fig. 2), meaning that glaciomarine sedimentation was established immediately upon deglaciation (López-Quirós et al., 2024). During this initial stage of FAZ-C (≥ 12.0 cal ka BP), the glaciomarine indicator species exhibit their highest relative abundance, followed by an overall decreasing

abundance towards the end of the zone (Fig. 3). The FAZ-C termination coincides with the end in the deposition of LU-IV (Fig. 5) described as the marine diamicton, determined to be deposited through enhanced ice rafting as the frontal calving zone of the ice shelf receded over the core site, marking the transition into a more distal glaciomarine (López-Quirós et al., 2024). Thus, the abundance of the glaciomarine indicators appears to correlate with the grounding line proximity and presence of ice shelves, as their relative abundance significantly decreases following the passage of the calving front (Fig. 3).

In Core 117G, FAZ-C (≥ 11.4 cal ka BP) displays a more limited abundance and temporal range of the glaciomarine indicator species (Figs. 3 and 5). This is likely a result of glaciomarine conditions first being established near the passage of the calving front (LU-IV) following

Fig. 5. PC1 and PC2 from the combined PCA are plotted against time for the analyzed cores. High positive and negative scoring species are displayed with their environmental color-coding corresponding to Fig. 3. The time ranges of the lithological units (LU-I to V), defined by López-Quirós et al. (2024) for the three cores, are indicated. The benthic foraminiferal assemblage zones (FAZ-A to C) are highlighted based on the PC1 and PC2 scores from the combined PCA, the benthic foraminiferal assemblages, and lithological units.

Table 3

Timing of the foraminiferal zones, based on the combined PCA, benthic foraminiferal assemblages, and lithological units, used in the description of the assemblage successions following shelf deglaciation.

Core	FAZ-C	FAZ-B	FAZ-A
DA17-NG-ST12-135G (outer shelf)	≥12.0 cal ka BP	12.0–7.7 cal ka BP	≤7.7 cal ka BP
DA17-NG-ST10-117G (middle shelf)	≥11.4 cal ka BP	11.4–6.1 cal ka BP	≤6.1 cal ka BP
DA17-NG-ST08-092G (inner shelf)	≥8.2 cal ka BP	8.2–5.8 cal ka BP	≤5.8 cal ka BP

the cessation of the mass wasting deposits (LU-VI) at the core site (Fig. 2) (López-Quirós et al., 2024). Notably, the abundance of the glaciomarine indicator species decreases following the calving front retreat, further indicating their affinity towards proximal glaciomarine conditions (Fig. 3).

The base of 92G is only speculated to have penetrated the glacial till and therefore may not reflect the glacial-deglacial transition (Davies et al., 2022; López-Quirós et al., 2024). However, the presence of LU-V at the onset of FAZ-C (≥8.2 cal ka BP) indicates proximal glaciomarine conditions (López-Quirós et al., 2024) with the zone still characterized by the abundance of the glaciomarine indicator species (Fig. 3). While López-Quirós et al. (2024) does not observe an ice-rafted diamicton

(LU-IV), signifying the exact passing of the calving front, local increases of ice-rafted debris are observed by Davies et al. (2022) to roughly align with the termination of FAZ-C, suggesting the presence of a nearby calving front. The zone termination occurs during the deposition of LU-III, marking the transition between proximal and open marine conditions (López-Quirós et al., 2024), during which the glaciomarine indicator species lose their assemblage dominance (Fig. 3). Thus, by 8.2 cal ka BP, the floating ice margin, precursing the modern ZI, would have been in the vicinity of the 92G core site. This may appear at odds with terrestrial reconstructions of the ice margin by Larsen et al. (2018), showing grounding line positions of the NEGIS inside its present-day limits (Fig. 6). This potentially contradictory coexistence could stem from differences in the dating approaches with the marine radiocarbon age model possibly being affected by unaccounted reservoir effects (Heaton et al., 2020, 2023), or that the terrestrial data show the grounding zone line, while the marine data may show the edge of the floating ice shelf.

5.1.3. Paleooceanographic changes – advection of Atlantic Water

While the sedimentological and hydroacoustic analyses conducted by López-Quirós et al. (2024) revealed ice-retreat dynamics in the Belgica Trough, paleooceanographic changes and their possible impact on the ice dynamics must be inferred from the benthic foraminiferal assemblage. Here, *C. neoteretis* is an indicator for presence of the warm

Fig. 6. Comparison of proxy records spanning the Deglaciation-Holocene. A: The mean summer insolation curve for 77°N (Laskar et al., 2004). B: The NGRIP ice core $\delta^{18}O$ record (NGRIP-Members, 2004). C: Reconstruction of the NEGIS margin (Larsen et al., 2018). D: Reconstruction of sea-ice conditions on the inner NEG shelf based on the P_BIP₂₅ index from core PS100/270, computed using brassicasterol as phytoplankton (Syring et al., 2020a). A superimposed 5-point running average has been calculated. E: Same as in D for core PS93/025 (Syring et al., 2020b) on the outer NEG shelf. F: PC1 from the combined PCA for the analyzed cores and timing of the benthic assemblage foraminiferal zones (FAZ-A to C). The time range of the lithological units (LU-I to V) for the three 92G, 117G, and 135G are indicated (López-Quirós et al., 2024). G: The relative abundance of *C. neoteretis* from core OCE2017-GR02-GC (Devendra et al., 2022) on the NEG slope and cores spanning from the outer NEG shelf, through the Belgica Trough, towards the inner shelf near the present-day margin of the ZI: DA17-NG-ST08-92G (Davies et al., 2022), DA17-NG-ST10-117G, DA17-NG-ST12-135G, PS100-198 GC (Lloyd et al., 2023), and PS100/270 (Syring et al., 2020a). A 5-point running average has been calculated for all the cores to highlight the time-transgressive decrease in AW (*C. neoteretis*) at the core sites on the shelf. See Fig. 1 for core locations. Abbreviations: LGM: Last Glacial Maximum; H1: Heinrich Stadial 1; B-A: Bølling-Allerød; YD: Younger Dryas.

and saline subsurface RAW at the NEG shelf, as this species predominates Arctic to North Atlantic benthic environments influenced by the warm and saline AW superimposed by surficial cold and low saline PW (Cage et al., 2021; Jennings et al., 2020a; Jennings and Helgadottir, 1994; Jennings and Weiner, 1996; Seidenkrantz, 1995; Wollenburg et al., 2004). The modern environmental affinity of *I. norcrossi* and *C. reniforme* is discussed by Devendra et al. (2022), relating its abundance to the contribution of AAW (Hald and Korsun, 1997; Jennings et al., 2004; Korsun and Polyak, 1989; Mudie et al., 1984; Sejrup et al., 1981). *C. reniforme* is able to thrive in colder water masses than *I. norcrossi* (Devendra et al., 2022; Ślubowska-Woldengen et al., 2007) and has been linked to the presence of PW in previous paleoceanographic reconstructions of the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023). However, the covariance between these two species along PC1 and PC2 in the combined PCA and their close clustering in the individual PCAs suggests that they relate to the same water mass (Fig. 4). Their covariance with *C. neoteretis* along PC2 in the combined PCA further indicates that these species relate to the advection of AW. It is therefore suggested that these three species are indicators of the different AW components on the NEG shelf, with *C. neoteretis* largely being an indicator of the warm RAW component while *I. norcrossi* and *C. reniforme* indicate the chilled AAW component in this region (Devendra et al., 2022).

The continuous abundance of these AW indicator species throughout FAZ-C across the core sites suggests that AW reached the Belgica Trough at the subsurface beneath the PW layer (Fig. 3). Core 135G displays the lowest occurrence of *C. neoteretis* relative to *I. norcrossi* and *C. reniforme*. This is probably due to the shallower water depth at the core site resulting in a higher prevalence of AAW whereas the 92G core site, exhibiting the greatest water depth, is subjected to a higher contribution of RAW (Håvik et al., 2017), indicated by the higher relative predominance of *C. neoteretis* (Fig. 3).

As core 135G captures the transition from glacial till to glaciomarine deposits (López-Quirós et al., 2024), the immediate presence of AW indicator species following deglaciation indicates the potential contribution of AW to the retreat of NEGIS through basal melting (Fig. 3). This is in accordance with Devendra et al. (2022) finding an increase in AW advection on the NEG slope from 18.5 cal ka BP, based on increasing abundance of *C. neoteretis* and lowered benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (Core OCE2017-GR02-GC; Fig. 1). The presence of AW being advected onto the shelf at this time is also recorded by core DA17-NG-ST01-019G in the inter-trough area between the Westwind and Belgica troughs (Fig. 1); this site was ice-free during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) (Rasmussen et al., 2022). López-Quirós et al. (2024) suggests the initiation of the shelf deglaciation to coincide with the subsurface warming during Heinrich Stadial 1 (H1). However, this warming is firstly recorded on the NEG slope during the later stages of H1 by 16.0 cal ka BP when shelf deglaciation had already initiated (Devendra et al., 2022). Hence, it appears to be the increase in AW advection after the LGM and prior to H1 that contributed to the onset of the shelf deglaciation. However, the subsurface AW influx during H1 likely accelerated this retreat as indicated in 135G after 16.0 cal ka BP by the slight increase in *C. neoteretis* together with the salinity indicator *T. trihedra* (Murray, 1991; Murray and Smart, 1994) and current indicator *C. lobatulus* (Wollenburg and Mackensen, 1998) (Fig. 3).

An accelerated retreat of the NEGIS is proposed during the Bølling-Allerød interstadial (López-Quirós et al., 2024), due to observations of regional subsurface warming (Aagaard-Sørensen et al., 2010; Consolaro et al., 2018; Rasmussen et al., 2007; Ślubowska-Woldengen et al., 2007) with the NEG slope experiencing enhanced AW advection by 14.0 cal ka BP (Devendra et al., 2022). An immediate shelf response to this slope condition is not obvious due to insignificant changes in AW indicator species in 135G (Fig. 3). However, the benthic assemblage yields an increase at 13.8 cal ka BP in concentration and fluxes concurring with high abundance of *T. trihedra* and *C. lobatulus*, suggesting a vigorous AW influx with an unchanged relative contribution of AAW and RAW

indicator species. In support of hereof, Hansen et al. (2022) record a concurrent vigorous influx of AW at the outer shelf in the Westwind Trough based on high abundance of *C. neoteretis* relative to AAW indicators. This influx likely accelerated the basal melting of the NEGIS, thereby facilitating increased foraminiferal fluxes through enhanced entrainment of nutrients by the increased production of upwelling, low-density subglacial meltwater plumes (cf. Meire et al., 2023).

Following the Bølling-Allerød, the poleward transport of AW decreased during the Younger Dryas stadial as a result of a weakened Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation likely due to the accumulated meltwater input from the retreating ice sheets (McManus et al., 2004; Spielhagen and Mackensen, 2021; Telesiński et al., 2014). Despite this reduction, AW indicators from the Belgica Trough together with other studies from the NEG shelf and slope still record the continued presence of AW, although weakened, flowing beneath the cold PW surface layer (Devendra et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2022). Changes in the benthic assemblages related to this study show an increasing abundance of AAW indicators relative to the RAW indicators, reflecting a weakened yet prevailing advection of AW (Fig. 3). Furthermore, the *T. trihedra* and *C. lobatulus* in these assemblage successions exhibit significant decreases, aligning with the observations of a lowered influx of RAW and a greater contribution from the cooler, less saline AAW.

During the Younger Dryas, readvances of NEGIS have been proposed by Arndt et al. (2017) based on the hydroacoustic analysis of grounding zone wedges in the Belgica Trough. However, López-Quirós et al. (2024) determine such a readvance unlikely due to the improved age control of the shelf deposits, aligning with recent reinvestigations of circum-GIS deposits displaying no evidence for Younger Dryas ice readvances (Funder et al., 2021). The benthic assemblages from the Belgica Trough corroborate with these recent findings, as the continued presence of the AW likely inhibited the possibility for a readvance of the NEGIS due to sustained basal melting (Fig. 3).

5.2. FAZ-B: productive, reduced sea-ice environment

Based on the lithological characteristics of LU-III and LU-II, FAZ-B covers the transition from glaciomarine to open marine conditions where sedimentation occurred as suspension settling from meltwater plumes (López-Quirós et al., 2024). The zone generally covers the Early Holocene climate amelioration, culminating with the Holocene Thermal Maximum with its timing in Greenland being based on marine and ice core records (Cartapanis et al., 2022; Kaufman, 2004; NGRIP-Members, 2004) (Fig. 6). In this ameliorated climatic setting, biomarker-based sea-ice reconstructions from the inner and outer NEG shelf yield a variable to reduced sea-ice cover concurring with intense phytoplankton productivity from 10.2 to 7.5 cal ka BP (Core PS93/025, PS100/270; Figs. 1 and 6) (Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b), aligning with circum-Arctic sea-ice reconstructions during the Holocene Thermal Maximum (Detlef et al., 2023; Devendra et al., 2023; Jakobsson et al., 2010).

5.2.1. Indicator species for productive, reduced sea-ice environment

The benthic assemblages across all core sites during FAZ-B are characterized by the distinct dominance of species thriving under enhanced nutrient supply such as *M. barleeanus* (Caralp, 1989; Polyak, 2002), *S. feylingi* (Knudsen and Seidenkrantz, 1994; Seidenkrantz, 2013), *A. weddellensis* (Gooday, 1993), *P. osloensis* (Rasmussen et al., 2003), *B. frigida* (Seidenkrantz, 2013; Strunk et al., 2018), *N. fragilis* (Davies et al., 2023; Gooday and Hughes, 2002), and *E. takayanagii* (Seidenkrantz et al., 2007). The abundance of these eutrophic species corroborates with the biomarker- and lithological-based reconstructions signifying a transition towards a highly productive environment with increased burial of organic material as the ice shelf time-transgressively retreated from the three core sites in Belgica Trough (López-Quirós et al., 2024; Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b). *M. barleeanus* is suggested to prefer degraded organic material (Caralp, 1989) while *S. feylingi* prefers

fresh phytodetritus (Seidenkrantz, 2013), indicating that both nutrient sources were abundantly available. The absolute dominance of this eutrophic assemblage has no analog to the modern setting of the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2023). However, *M. barleeanus* and *E. clavatum* are observed abundant among the modern calcareous assemblage in the NEW polynya, where productivity and organic burial are increased, thereby supporting the interpretation of a productive environment (Davies et al., 2023; Newton and Rowe, 1995; Syring et al., 2020b). The pronounced decrease of the glaciomarine indicators in this zone further corroborates with the retreat of the floating ice shelf, marking the transition into seasonal sea-ice conditions at the core sites (López-Quirós et al., 2024; Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b). The eutrophic response in the benthic foraminiferal assemblage is also recorded in multiple other cores across the NEG shelf, indicating this assemblage succession as a consistent response to a productive and reduced sea-ice paleoenvironment (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a).

The setting of a highly productive environment is also conveyed by the ecological traits of the assemblages in FAZ-B (Hansen et al., 2023). Here, the abundance of *S. feylingi* and *M. barleeanus* point towards dys-oxic to suboxic bottom conditions likely caused by the degradation of the increased organic flux to the seabed (Hansen et al., 2023; Van Der Zwaan et al., 1999). In support hereof, López-Quirós et al. (2024) found elevated elemental counts of barium in the deposits related to FAZ-B across core sites which are proposed to be sensitive indicators of surface water paleoproductivity. Despite this elevated food supply, the foraminiferal concentrations and fluxes remain low compared to the previous sub-ice shelf setting of FAZ-C, indicating that the low oxygen levels comprise the limiting factor for the foraminiferal abundance (Hansen et al., 2023; Van Der Zwaan et al., 1999). Hence, FAZ-B appears to comprise a specialized benthic foraminiferal assemblage in which mainly the eutrophic species are able to thrive under these productive conditions (Davies et al., 2022).

5.2.2. Paleooceanographic changes

The paleooceanographic changes throughout FAZ-B in all cores present a continuous declining presence of AW marked by the declining abundance of AW indicators together with the concurrent decrease in salinity indicators (Fig. 3). This stands in contrast to the conditions on the NEG slope where a significant increase in *C. neoteretis* indicates vigorous AW advection throughout the Holocene Thermal Maximum, culminating at 6.8 cal ka BP (Devendra et al., 2022) (Fig. 6), aligning with the expansion of warm AW into the Nordic seas and further into the eastern Fram Strait (Consolaro et al., 2018; Devendra et al., 2023; Koç et al., 1993; Rasmussen et al., 2007). Similarly, AW prevails longer in the Westwind Trough compared to the Belgica Trough, peaking at 7.5 to 6.7 cal ka BP (Core DA17-NG-ST03-039, PS93/025; Fig. 1) (Hansen et al., 2022; Zehnich et al., 2020), see section 5.3 for the discussion of these discrepancies. However, despite its declining presence in the Belgica Trough, AW likely contributed, in combination with the peak atmospheric insolation (Laskar et al., 2004), to reduced sea-ice conditions and the continued retreat of the NEGIS, reaching its minimum extent 70 km behind the present margin between 7.8 and 4.6 cal ka BP (Bennike and Weidick, 2001; Larsen et al., 2018) (Fig. 6).

5.3. FAZ-A: expanding sea ice and declining AW shelf advection

The lithological units of FAZ-A include LU-II and LU-I deposited in an open marine setting through hemipelagic deposition (López-Quirós et al., 2024). In all cores, the zone concurs within the range of the well-established Mid to Late Holocene cooling that followed the termination of the Holocene Thermal Maximum in Northeast Greenland around 7.0–5.0 cal ka BP (Kaufman, 2004; Laskar et al., 2004) (Fig. 6). This Neoglacial cooling is characterized by minimum solar insolation (Laskar et al., 2004), enhanced export of Arctic drift ice by the EGC

(Andrews et al., 2009; Cabedo-Sanz et al., 2016), and overall southward migration of the polar front (Bauch et al., 2001; Koç et al., 1993). Locally, an extensive, near perennial sea-ice cover formed on the inner NEG shelf by 7.5 cal ka BP while the outer shelf gradually transitioned into a seasonal to marginal sea-ice cover from 7.9 cal ka BP until the formation of the NEW polynya by 1 cal ka BP (Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b) (Fig. 6). Paleooceanographic studies, based on benthic foraminiferal assemblages, from the NEG shelf record significant drops in sedimentation rates and assemblage dominance of agglutinated taxa which are used to infer increased advection of PW resulting in cold, corrosive bottom water conditions (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a).

5.3.1. Formation of corrosive bottom waters

5.3.1.1. Advection of Polar Water. The paleooceanographic studies from the NEG shelf recording advection of PW, leading to cold, corrosive bottom water conditions in the Mid to Late Holocene (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a) are strongly supported by the cores from the Belgica Trough. Here, the assemblages of FAZ-A are characterized by the lowest foraminiferal concentrations, pronounced drops in sedimentation rates, and the near disappearance of calcareous taxa, replaced by the complete dominance of agglutinated taxa (Figs. 2 and 3). We are aware that the low foraminiferal concentrations in this zone could be an artifact of sediment compaction due to the concentration being based on wet sample volumes. However, the computed density logs for the analyzed cores appear to correlate with actual lithological variations rather than core depth (López-Quirós et al., 2024). Further, the foraminiferal fluxes, accounting for compactional effects on the sedimentation rate, exhibit fluctuating values throughout the cores rather than varying systematically with core depth (Fig. 3). Moreover, Davies et al. (2023) showed that while a few calcareous specimens may be found at sites today impacted by PW, their number is low and they disappear immediately below the sediment surface. Therefore, we consider the immediate post-mortem dissolution of calcareous taxa in a cold, corrosive environment to be the primary cause for the low foraminiferal concentrations, resulting in the preferential preservation of agglutinated taxa in the sedimentological record.

The timing of FAZ-A exhibits a time transgressive initiation from the outer NEG shelf at 7.7 cal ka BP in 135G to the inner shelf at 5.8 cal ka BP in 92G (Fig. 5). The abundance of agglutinated species such as *L. difflugiformis* (Jennings and Helgadottir, 1994; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022), *P. bipolaris* (Lloyd, 2006), and *T. earlandi* (Lloyd, 2006; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Wangner et al., 2018) is associated with low-saline, cold water conditions. This suggests that the advection of AW was severely reduced or completely halted, replaced by a prevalent influx of PW reaching the seabed that time-transgressively propagated from the outer Belgica Trough to its inner part. Due to PW having a lower temperature and higher solubility of carbon dioxide, i.e. lower pH, this advection likely resulted in corrosive bottom water conditions, facilitating the dissolution of calcareous taxa (Aksu, 1983).

The presence of *A. globigeriniformis* further supports the interpretation of corrosive bottom water conditions, as it is found abundant among agglutinated species in low pH conditions (Panieri et al., 2005). Hence, the predominance of agglutinated taxa and low calcareous concentration in FAZ-A aligns with the other paleooceanographic studies on the NEG shelf in concluding a Mid to Late Holocene transition towards cold, corrosive bottom water conditions (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a). This increased advection of PW likely assisted the lowered solar insolation in facilitating the expansion of the sea-ice conditions (Davies et al., 2022; Laskar et al., 2004; Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b) (Fig. 6).

To further examine and explain the corrosive conditions caused by the advection of PW, the paleoceanography of the Belgica Trough should be compared with the paleoceanographic development on the immediate slope. Based on the abundance of *C. neoteretis* and benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, Devendra et al. (2022) find that the inflow of RAW significantly increased on the slope at ca. 10 cal. ka BP whereas the AW indicators on the outer Belgica Trough in 135G exhibit a contemporary decreasing inflow, culminating in FAZ-A (Fig. 6). As noted by Devendra et al. (2022), this apparent discrepancy must be resolved by decoupling the inflow of AW on the slope from the shelf. Therefore, the inflow of RAW on the slope likely protruded into greater depths and was unable to reach the shallower waters of the shelf. The accumulated meltwater masses from the GIS and PW inflow from the EGC possibly formed a strong pycnocline, separating the deeper-lying RAW from the overlying cold, low-saline PW layer. This decoupling enables the time-transgressive response in the benthic foraminiferal assemblages as the intrusion of PW was initiated at the outer Belgica Trough and progressed towards its inner areas. Supporting this interpretation is the fact that a time-transgressive response of declining AW inflow can be consistently tracked from the cores in this study to core PS100-198 on the very inner Belgica Trough (Lloyd et al., 2023) and even further to core PS100/270, situated directly at the modern terminus of the 79NG (Syring et al., 2020a) (Fig. 6). A severely reduced inflow of AW is also observed after 10.9 cal ka BP further south on the East Greenland Shelf off Young Sound (Core DA17-NG-ST14-171G; Fig. 1), indicating a region-wide pattern of the shelf decoupling from slope inflow (Jackson et al., 2022). In addition, a study from the Southwest Svalbard shelf reports the formation of a Mid to Late Holocene strong pycnocline separating bottom-flowing warm AW from a sea ice-rich cold surface layer (Devendra et al., 2023), providing an analogy for a similar process occurring on the NEG shelf.

5.3.1.2. Degradation of organic matter. Although the influx of PW appears a likely candidate in explaining the development of corrosive bottom conditions in FAZ-A, other potential factors should be examined. Here, it is possible that the accumulated degradation of the previous organic fluxes from the elevated productive conditions during the HTM resulted in sub to dysoxic seabed conditions and elevated levels of dissolved carbon dioxide, thereby facilitating these corrosive conditions (Davies et al., 2023; Hansen et al., 2023; Van Der Zwaan et al., 1999). However, such an accumulated effect appears unlikely since foraminiferal traits analysis of 135G indicates FAZ-A to comprise a rather oxic-preferring assemblage than FAZ-B (Hansen et al., 2023). Thus, degradation of organic matter seems insufficient in explaining the corrosive seabed conditions.

5.3.1.3. Expanding sea ice and brine rejection. Another plausible cause for the formation of corrosive bottom waters on the NEG shelf in the Mid to Late Holocene (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a) involves intensified brine rejection from the Mid to Late Holocene expanding sea-ice conditions. Brines, which are cold, saline, and enriched in dissolved carbon dioxide, are able to produce a highly corrosive benthic environment (Fossile et al., 2020; Rasmussen and Thomsen, 2014). Hence, the agglutinated to calcareous taxa ratio has been applied as a proxy for reconstructing past brine formation (Rasmussen and Thomsen, 2014; Seidenkrantz, 2013; Seidenkrantz et al., 2007; Steinsund and Hald, 1994). For brine rejection to explain the agglutinated predominance of FAZ-A, there should be a distinctive difference in this ratio among the sediment cores from the inner and outer Belgica Trough. Here, the near perennial sea-ice conditions on the inner shelf, along with the establishment of the NØIB, would facilitate improved preservation of calcareous taxa compared to the more brine-influenced marginal sea-ice conditions on the outer shelf (Davies et al., 2023; Syring et al., 2020a). This aligns with observations of

modern foraminiferal assemblages on the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2023) and shelf distribution of water column pCO_2 measurements (Willcox et al., 2024). However, no such difference is observed, as the cores from Belgica Trough show agglutinated taxa reaching comparable abundances, exceeding 90 % (Fig. 3). Similarly, other cores from the NEG shelf do not reflect a significant Mid to Late Holocene spatial variability in the calcareous preservation across its inner and outer areas (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a; Zehlich et al., 2020). Thus, brine rejection also appears unable to explain the rise of corrosive bottom conditions in FAZ-A.

While a time-transgressive PW intrusion appears as the most consistent explanation for the benthic foraminiferal response to the paleoceanographic development in the Belgica Trough, brine rejection may be able to explain local assemblage differences within the trough. Here, cores from the very inner part still show some presence of AW indicators after the pronounced decrease (Lloyd et al., 2023; Syring et al., 2020a), whereas these indicators almost completely disappear on the outer trough in 135G (Fig. 6). These differences may be due to the carbonate-preserving conditions facilitated by the formation of the near-perennial NØIB (Syring et al., 2020a). However, it cannot explain the consistent time-transgressive decrease in AW inflow propagating from the outer to the inner trough. Also, cores on the inner Belgica Trough provide a higher temporal resolution of the Late Holocene paleoceanographic development, showing increases in AW indicators as early as 1.5 cal ka BP, marking the return of AW inflow to the NEG shelf and the transition towards its modern setting (Davies et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Syring et al., 2020a) (Fig. 6). However, in core 117G and 135G, despite the age models assigning the uppermost foraminiferal samples ages of 0.9 and 0.1 cal ka BP, respectively, this development remains poorly resolved, likely caused by the poor age control and low temporal resolution of the latest part of the Holocene (Figs. 2 and 3).

5.3.1.4. Temporal offset between the Belgica and Westwind Trough. Finally, it should be noted that the decoupling of AW inflow exhibits a significant temporal offset between the outer Belgica Trough in 135G at 10 cal. ka BP and the outer Westwind Trough between 7.5 and 6.7 cal ka BP (Hansen et al., 2022; Zehlich et al., 2020). This offset may be explained by AAW being the main AW source in the Westwind Trough instead of RAW (Schaffer et al., 2017), which dominates the Belgica Trough. AAW is situated shallower in the water column (Håvik et al., 2017; Schaffer et al., 2017; Willcox et al., 2023), potentially delaying the timing for this flow to reach the required depths for slope decoupling. However, the few available cores from the Westwind Trough along with their restricted spatial coverage complicate a similar time-transgressive assessment of its paleoceanographic development. Therefore, it is difficult to fully disclose the cause behind this temporal offset between the troughs.

5.4. Benthic foraminifera as a proxy for deglaciation

The individual PCAs of the three sediment cores display similar clusters of glaciomarine, productivity, and agglutinated indicator species (Fig. 4). This suggests that the Deglacial-Holocene benthic ecosystem response at each core site is driven by comparable assemblage variability (Figs. 3 and 4). This similar clustering further validates the loadings scores of species in the combined PCA as being representative of driving the assemblage variability across the core sites (Fig. 5). Consequently, the successive scoring trends for PC1 and PC2 in the combined PCA evidently demonstrate a consistent time-transgressive response of the benthic foraminifera assemblages in the Belgica Trough to the deglaciation of the NEG shelf (Fig. 5).

Based on this time-transgressive behavior of the assemblages and PC scores, the combined PCA enables a consistent zonation to establish a conceptual characterization of the benthic foraminiferal response to the

deglaciation of the NEG shelf (Fig. 7). Here, the foraminiferal assemblages exhibit consistent assemblage succession, with the timing of their development (zonation) across core sites corresponding well with past environmental change established through independent analyses by López-Quirós et al. (2024). In FAZ-C, the sedimentological evidence of the past ice dynamics reveals the presence of a sub-ice shelf environment that corroborates with the glaciomarine characteristics of the benthic foraminiferal assemblages, particularly highlighted by the zone termination coinciding with the passage of the calving front at core 117G and 135G (López-Quirós et al., 2024) (Figs. 6 and 7). The subsequent transition to a eutrophic-dominated assemblage in FAZ-B links to a productive, reduced sea-ice environment inferred from direct sea-ice proxies and the overall ameliorated climatic conditions (Laskar et al., 2004; NGRIP-Members, 2004; Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b) (Figs. 6 and 7). Further, the time-transgressive decrease of AW indicator species and rising dominance of agglutinated taxa in FAZ-A provides strong evidence for paleoceanographic change in the Belgica Trough, showing PW replacing the inflow of AW (Davies et al., 2022; Devendra et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Syring et al., 2020a) (Figs. 6 and 7). Altogether these consistent time-transgressive responses highlight the sensibility of benthic foraminifera towards the complex interplay between ice dynamics, ecological conditions, and ocean variability, proving the reliability of the proxy in reconstructing deglaciated marine environments.

5.4.1. Statistical uncertainty

This study applies a relatively low counting threshold of 30 specimens to maximize the inclusion of assemblage data points in the analysis of the benthic ecosystem responses to the deglaciation of the NEG shelf. In Arctic studies, lowered counting thresholds can be a necessary practice due to low foraminiferal content in Arctic marine sediments (Davies et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023). However, this approach comes with a trade-off, as lowered counts introduce greater

statistical uncertainty. Based on the works by Patterson and Fishbein (1989), counting only 30 specimens potentially exhibits relative abundance uncertainties reaching up to 8–16% for species comprising 5–70% of the assemblage. However, despite this study applying a threshold of 30 counts, most samples contain significantly higher counts (c. 200 on average for core 135G and 117G, and c. 300 for 92G; Supplementary Material), substantially reducing these uncertainties (Patterson and Fishbein, 1989).

Nevertheless, it is still important to evaluate whether statistical uncertainties jeopardize the validity of the observed time-transgressive response patterns of the benthic foraminiferal assemblage successions. We argue that this is unlikely due to three main reasons. First, the response patterns in the benthic foraminiferal assemblages are well constrained by independent paleoenvironmental reconstructions of the NEG shelf, supporting the reliability of the results presented in this study (López-Quirós et al., 2024; Syring et al., 2020a, 2020b) (Figs. 6 and 7). Second, although the benthic foraminiferal counts fluctuate by 1–2 orders of magnitude within each FAZ (Supplementary Material), we consistently observe gradual evolutionary trends in benthic assemblage successions across the core sites: a gradual decrease in glaciomarine indicator species as the ice-shelf retreats past the core sites, followed by a gradual increase in eutrophic indicator species, replaced by the rising dominance of agglutinated taxa (Figs. 3 and 7). These trends are not indicative of systematic errors caused by large statistical uncertainties from samples with low foraminiferal counts. Third, the FAZs are representative of three distinct environmental settings (Fig. 7), which effectively lowers the specimen counts required to reliably detect significant changes in assemblage successions (Patterson and Fishbein, 1989). This is likely an important contributing factor in explaining the clear and consistent time-transgressive response of the benthic foraminifera to the deglaciation of the NEG shelf, despite using a low counting threshold.

Fig. 7. Conceptualized reconstruction of the benthic foraminiferal response in the Belgica Trough to the deglaciation and Holocene environmental conditions of the NEG shelf. The initial deglacial succession (FAZ-C) is dominated by benthic species with an environmental preference towards glaciomarine conditions (blue curve), characterizing a benthic foraminiferal assemblage beneath a floating ice shelf with inflow of AW at the bottom (red arrow; AW indicator species are color-indicated: Return Atlantic Water (red) and Chilled Atlantic Water (orange)). The assemblage is then dominated by a specialized eutrophic species assemblage (green curve), indicating a high-productive environment with seasonal sea ice (FAZ-B), culminating in the Early Holocene. The inflow of AW is decreasing, replaced by PW (blue arrow). In the Mid to Late Holocene, the foraminiferal succession becomes dominated by agglutinated taxa (grey curve) in an environment characterized by expanding sea-ice conditions and strong advection of PW (FAZ-A), promoting corrosive bottom water conditions and dissolution of calcareous taxa.

5.5. Standard assemblages in deglacial successions

The reliability of benthic foraminifera as proxies, demonstrated by this study, allows for the evaluation of standard assemblages for the different stages in a deglacial succession.

5.5.1. Early deglaciation assemblages

On the NEG shelf, relatively high abundances of *S. horvathi* are characteristic of the early stages of deglaciation (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a) (Fig. 3). This species is also documented to comprise assemblages in several other locations around Greenland, including the Baffin Bay (Sheldon et al., 2016) and Smith Sound (Jennings et al., 2019), and in the Canadian Arctic, including the Barrow Strait (Pieńkowski et al., 2012, 2013, 2014) and Lancaster Sound (Furze et al., 2018), when proximal sub-ice shelf conditions prevailed during the initial deglacial stages regardless of the dominant bottom water masses. Similarly, *S. concava* is also abundant in early deglacial assemblages in the Baffin Bay (Sheldon et al., 2016), Denmark Strait (Jennings et al., 2011a), Nares Strait (Jennings et al., 2011b), and Smith Sound (Jennings et al., 2019), while the recently identified species *G. oculus* (Jennings et al., 2020b) is also documented in early deglacial assemblages in Lancaster Sound (Kelleher et al., 2022). The consistent abundance of these species across these Arctic regions thus suggests they constitute standard assemblages for proximal glaciomarine conditions during early deglaciation (Fig. 7).

Despite *Miliolinella subrotunda* being abundant in the early deglacial stages on the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2022) (Fig. 3), documentation of its distribution in early deglacial assemblages across other Arctic regions appears limited. A study from the Nares Strait (Jennings et al., 2011b) shows this species to be abundant in Early to Mid Holocene assemblages during distal glaciomarine to productive conditions. Likewise, deglacial successions from the Nares Strait (Georgiadis et al., 2020), Smith Sound (Jennings et al., 2019), and the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2022) (Fig. 3) indicate *E. arctica* to be a versatile species with an affinity towards both glaciomarine and productive paleoenvironments. Hence, these two species do not appear to comprise standard indicators for proximal glaciomarine conditions.

Early deglacial assemblages in the Svalbard-Barents Sea region differ notably from those found in the Canadian Arctic and Greenland. Here, the assemblages containing *S. concava* and *S. horvathi* exhibit little to no abundance (Devendra et al., 2023; Polyak and Solheim, 1994; Rasmussen et al., 2007, 2013; Rasmussen and Thomsen, 2014; Skirbekk et al., 2010; Ślubowska et al., 2005; Ślubowska-Woldengen et al., 2007). These assemblages are instead dominated by the opportunistic *E. clavatum* and *C. reniforme*, signifying weakened AW inflow. *S. loeblichii* is also commonly present in these assemblages (Devendra et al., 2023; Rasmussen et al., 2013; Skirbekk et al., 2010; Ślubowska et al., 2005), indicating glaciomarine conditions with extensive sea-ice cover. *S. loeblichii* appears more commonly and abundantly in this region compared to Greenland and the Canadian Arctic (Furze et al., 2018; Hansen et al., 2020; Jennings et al., 2011a, 2011b, 2019; Pieńkowski et al., 2012, 2013, 2014; Sheldon et al., 2016). These assemblage differences could potentially be linked to differences in the deglacial paleoenvironmental settings where ice shelves were present in Greenland and the Canadian Arctic (Furze et al., 2018; López-Quirós et al., 2024), as opposed to the presence of marine-terminating ice streams in the Svalbard-Barents Sea region (Ingólfsson and Landvik, 2013).

5.5.2. Early Holocene assemblages

Assemblages for the ameliorated conditions during the Early Holocene on the NEG shelf (Fig. 3) share distinct similarities with other Arctic regions. Particularly, the dominance of *S. feylingi* and *M. barleeanus* are found in several other cores around Greenland (Hansen et al., 2020; Jennings et al., 2011a, 2019; Sheldon et al., 2016). In the Baffin Bay

(Sheldon et al., 2016) and in the Denmark Strait (Jennings et al., 2011a), these coexist with *P. osloensis*, *A. weddellensis*, and *B. frigida*, thereby providing similar standard assemblages for the indication of eutrophic conditions in the Early Holocene. In the Canadian Arctic, *S. feylingi* and *B. frigida* are also commonly abundant among Early Holocene eutrophic assemblages (Furze et al., 2018; Gregory et al., 2010; Pieńkowski et al., 2012, 2013, 2014). While *M. barleeanus* is also present, it is typically less abundant than the aforementioned species which is in contrast to the assemblages around Greenland (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2020; Jennings et al., 2011a, 2019; Sheldon et al., 2016). Further, the eutrophic assemblages from the Canadian Arctic (Pieńkowski et al., 2012, 2013, 2014) and NW-SE Greenland (Gregory et al., 2010; Hansen et al., 2020; Jennings et al., 2011a, 2019) also exhibit a more consistent abundance of *N. labradorica* contrary to the NEG shelf (Davies et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2022; Lloyd et al., 2023; Pados-Dibattista et al., 2022; Syring et al., 2020a), suggesting this species to be a standard indicator of productive conditions in those areas. In the Svalbard-Barents Sea region, Early Holocene assemblages during ameliorated conditions also display similarities to those around Greenland and the Canadian Arctic due to the abundance and concurrence of *M. barleeanus*, *B. frigida*, *N. labradorica* although *S. feylingi* appears scarce (Devendra et al., 2023; Polyak and Solheim, 1994; Rasmussen et al., 2007, 2013; Rasmussen and Thomsen, 2014; Skirbekk et al., 2010; Ślubowska et al., 2005; Ślubowska-Woldengen et al., 2007). The comparisons made herein demonstrate that, whilst some regional variability exists, these Arctic regions exhibit similar abundances of eutrophic species during ameliorated conditions, providing a reliable standard for recognizing such paleoenvironments in a deglacial succession (Fig. 7).

5.5.3. Mid to Late Holocene assemblages

The deteriorating conditions during the Mid to Late Holocene on the NEG shelf are accompanied by the assemblage dominance of agglutinated taxa, marking the inflow of PW and promotion of carbonate dissolution (Figs. 3 and 7). This assemblage development is a region-wide feature observed around Greenland (Georgiadis et al., 2020; Hansen et al., 2020; Jackson et al., 2022; Jennings et al., 2011a, 2019; Sheldon et al., 2016) and also in the Barrow Strait (Gregory et al., 2010) and is attributed by the studies to the formation of cold corrosive bottom waters. Across these locations, the assemblages also share similar occurrences of agglutinated species, including *L. difflugiformis*, *P. bipolaris*, *T. earlandi* and *A. globigeriniformis*, thereby indicating this assemblage development to comprise an indicator for corrosive bottom water conditions.

In the Svalbard-Barents Sea region, transitions to agglutinated dominated assemblages are scarce (Devendra et al., 2023; Polyak and Solheim, 1994; Rasmussen et al., 2007; Skirbekk et al., 2010; Ślubowska et al., 2005; Ślubowska-Woldengen et al., 2007). Instead, these Mid to Late Holocene assemblages retain the abundance of calcareous taxa, characterized by the declining abundance of eutrophic and AW indicator species and rising abundance of *E. clavatum*, signifying the formation of a strong pycnocline with a less vigorous, yet persistent inflow of AW flowing beneath PW in a paleoenvironment with recovering sea ice (Devendra et al., 2023). This persistent inflow of AW, although less vigorous, points to generally warmer bottom conditions in the Svalbard-Barents Sea region likely caused by the shallower flow depth of the WSC (Cottier et al., 2005; Skogseth et al., 2020) enabling AW to influence the study sites. The occurrences of agglutinated dominated assemblages appear restricted to fjord systems where corrosive bottom water conditions are caused by the intensified production of brines during periods of expanding sea-ice conditions and weakened AW inflow (Rasmussen et al., 2013; Rasmussen and Thomsen, 2014). These brine-related assemblages present a similar abundance of agglutinated species as those around Greenland (Georgiadis et al., 2020; Hansen et al., 2020; Jackson et al., 2022; Jennings et al., 2011a, 2019; Sheldon et al., 2016) and the Barrow Strait (Gregory et al., 2010) which are the

result of AW being replaced by PW. Hence, the comparison demonstrates that the rising dominance of agglutinated taxa is a possible standard for identifying both scenarios. It is therefore critical that local environmental factors such as sea-ice variability are considered when determining the cause behind the transition from calcareous to agglutinated in a deglacial succession. As shown in this study, region-wide comparisons may enable this distinction between the assemblage succession being related to paleoceanographic changes or localized impacts from sea-ice variability (Fig. 6).

6. Conclusions

This study investigates the response of the benthic foraminiferal assemblages to the deglaciation of the Northeast Greenland shelf based on the analysis of three marine sediment cores, constituting a transect through the Belgica Trough. Three benthic foraminiferal assemblage zones delineate the presented reconstruction.

FAZ-C comprises the lowermost zone and is characterized by a sub-ice shelf environment forming subsequent to the deglaciation of the core sites with oxygenated bottom waters and low eutrophic levels. This is reflected by the abundance of glaciomarine indicator species *S. horvathi*, *S. concava*, and *G. oculus*. Bottom advection of AW is reflected by the presence of *C. neoteretis*, *C. reniforme*, and *I. norcrossi*, highlighting its potential contribution to ice retreat through basal melting.

FAZ-B occurs within an environment of reduced sea ice and overall ameliorated conditions during the Early Holocene. The productive environment likely caused low oxygenated bottom water conditions due to the degradation of elevated concentrations of organic matter. These conditions are reflected by the dominance of eutrophic and suboxic-tolerant indicator species such as *M. barleeanus*, *S. feylingi*, and *A. weddellensis*.

FAZ-A is associated with the subsequent climatic deterioration during the Mid to Late Holocene in an environment hosting an extensive sea-ice cover and a strong advection of PW replaced the AW inflow, promoting corrosive bottom water conditions. This setting is corroborated in the benthic foraminiferal assemblages, exhibiting dissolution of calcareous taxa and the rising dominance of agglutinated species *L. difflugiformis*, *P. bipolaris*, and *T. earlandi* being tolerant to cold, corrosive bottom water conditions. The time-transgressive response in the benthic foraminiferal assemblages provides evidence that the shelf inflow of AW was decoupled from the main advection on the slope, resulting in a time-transgressive PW intrusion that propagated from the outer trough towards its inner part.

The results of the study reveal a consistent time-transgressive assemblage succession across the core sites. This response demonstrates the sensitivity of benthic foraminifera towards the complex interaction between ice dynamics, ecological conditions, and ocean variability, proving their reliability as a proxy for both paleoenvironmental and paleoceanographic reconstructions. It also reveals an overall similar development of benthic foraminiferal assemblages in comparable environments thus inferring that benthic foraminiferal assemblages are indeed strong and reliable indicators of specific Arctic glaciomarine environments. Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of applying well-dated age-depth models for reconstructing past environments, as the successive nature of these responses would have otherwise remained unrevealed.

The demonstrated proxy reliability of benthic foraminifera enables the potential of identifying standard assemblages to characterize specific stages in deglacial successions. With comparison drawn to other Arctic regions, *S. horvathi*, *S. concava*, and *G. oculus* appear as important constituents in a standard assemblage for recognizing sub-ice shelf conditions. The comparison further reveals that productive paleoenvironments associated with reduced sea-ice cover during ameliorated conditions in the Arctic exhibit abundances of *M. barleeanus* and *S. feylingi* along with concurrence of other eutrophic species,

providing a reliable standard for recognizing such settings. Finally, the rising dominance of agglutinated species may comprise a standard for the identification of corrosive bottom water conditions caused by changes in the advection of bottom water masses or by enhanced brine rejection from sea ice. As demonstrated by this study, regional comparisons may enable the distinction between these two scenarios.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mads Ramsgaard Stoltenberg: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Tuomas Junna:** Formal analysis, Investigation. **Joanna Davies:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Karoline Kristensen:** Formal analysis, Investigation. **Katrine Elnegaard Hansen:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Christof Pearce:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Cruise participation, and Core retrieval, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Cruise planning and Leading, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2025.109407>.

Data availability

The foraminiferal data for 135G and 117G is available in the supplementary material. Foraminiferal data for 92G is already made available in [Davies et al. \(2022\)](#). Additional data will be made available on request.

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